

Distributed Estimation and Task-Driven Relational Formation Reconfiguration in Soccer Teams

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Abstract—This report studies soccer formation coordination from a multi-agent control perspective. Instead of treating consensus as all players converging to the same state, I model a team formation as a task-dependent relational structure, where players maintain important tactical distances and role-based constraints under local information.

To address the fact that players do not have full global knowledge, I propose a distributed estimation-control framework: each player estimates a latent team state from local observations, updates a task-dependent tactical graph, and then performs projected local adjustments to reduce formation error while respecting role feasibility. A small defensive-block simulation is designed to show how the proposed framework can recover compactness after disturbances and reconfigure the formation when the tactical task changes.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Multi-agent coordination studies how a group of agents can achieve collective behavior through local interactions. In a classical consensus problem, each agent updates its state by using information from its neighbors, and the interaction graph determines whether agreement can be reached and how fast the disagreement decays [1]. This viewpoint gives a useful mathematical language for studying distributed teamwork, especially when a fully centralized decision-making structure is not realistic.

Soccer is a natural example of a human multi-agent system. Each player makes decisions based on local perception, teammate movement, opponent pressure, and tactical instructions. However, soccer also shows why standard point consensus is not enough. A good team does not require all players to converge to the same position or perform the same role. Instead, the team needs formation-level consistency: players should preserve meaningful spacing, maintain role-dependent structure, and move coherently under a shared tactical intention.

In the earlier stages of this project, I modeled formation consensus through role-dependent anchors and formation-aligned variables. This gave a first way to measure whether the team was compact and coordinated. However, a fixed formation template is still too limited for real soccer. In pressing, transition, or defensive recovery, the desired formation itself changes. For example, when a fullback steps forward to press, the center back and defensive midfielder should not simply return to their original locations; they should adjust their relative positions to keep the whole defensive structure balanced.

Therefore, this final report moves from an absolute formation template to a relational formation model. In this model, the team shape is represented by a weighted tactical graph. The nodes represent players, and the edges represent important player-to-player tactical relations. The desired distances and edge weights are allowed to depend on the current task, so the formation can change when the game situation changes. This is closer to how soccer is actually played: a formation is not only a set of fixed coordinates, but a moving structure of responsibilities and relationships.

Based on this motivation, this report proposes a distributed estimation-control framework for task-driven formation reconfiguration. Since no player has full global information, each player first estimates a latent team state from local observations. This estimated state is then used to update the task-dependent tactical graph, and each player performs projected local adjustments to reduce relational formation error while respecting role feasibility. In this framework, the coach is not treated as a centralized controller who directly commands every player. Instead, the coach is modeled as a bounded meta-designer who shapes feasible interaction weights, task priorities, and tactical constraints.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Team and Player Model

We consider a soccer team with n players, indexed by

$$\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}.$$

Each player is treated as an agent with a physical position, a movement state, and a tactical role variable. For player i , let

$$p_i(k) \in \mathbb{R}^2$$

denote the position on the field at time step k , and let

$$x_i(k) = \begin{bmatrix} p_i(k) \\ v_i(k) \\ r_i(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

denote the local state of the player, where $v_i(k)$ is the velocity and $r_i(k)$ represents the role or tactical tendency. In this report, the team is modeled as a distributed system rather than a centralized one. Each player updates its behavior based on nearby teammates, opponent pressure, and the current tactical task.

Figure 2 illustrates this player-level state model. The position $p_i(k)$ describes where the player is located on the field, the velocity $v_i(k)$ captures the player's current movement, and the variable $r_i(k)$ represents the tactical identity of the

Overview of the Proposed Distributed Estimation-Control Framework

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed distributed estimation-control framework. Each player starts from local observations, participates in distributed estimation of the team state, updates a task-dependent tactical graph, and then performs projected local control to support formation reconfiguration. The coach acts as a bounded meta-designer by shaping task priorities, graph weights, and tactical constraints.

player, such as center back, defensive midfielder, or fullback. This simple state description is enough for the purpose of this report, since the main focus is not low-level biomechanics, but how local player states participate in team-level coordination and reconfiguration.

B. Local Observation and Latent Team State

Different from a fully centralized model, we do not assume that every player directly knows the full team state. Instead, we introduce a latent team state

$$\xi(k) = \begin{bmatrix} c(k) \\ \psi(k) \\ \ell(k) \\ \theta(k) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $c(k)$ denotes the formation center, $\psi(k)$ denotes the formation orientation, $\ell(k)$ describes compactness or shape parameters, and $\theta(k)$ denotes the tactical mode or strategy parameter.

Player i only receives a local observation

$$y_i(k) = H_i(k)\xi(k) + v_i^{\text{obs}}(k),$$

Fig. 2. Illustration of the local state of player i . The state includes the player position $p_i(k)$, movement/velocity $v_i(k)$, and role-dependent tactical variable $r_i(k)$.

where $H_i(k)$ is the local observation matrix and $v_i^{\text{obs}}(k)$ is the observation noise. Based on this local information, each player

Fig. 3. Local observation and distributed estimation structure. Each player only observes nearby teammates, opponents, and ball-related information inside a limited sensing region, so the global team state must be inferred in a distributed way.

maintains its own estimate

$$\hat{\xi}_i(k).$$

Therefore, one important part of the problem is to make the team form a sufficiently consistent understanding of the current team state through distributed estimation.

To measure disagreement among local estimates, we define

$$\Psi_G(\hat{\xi}(k)) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}(k)} \|\hat{\xi}_i(k) - \hat{\xi}_j(k)\|^2.$$

A small value of Ψ_G means that the players have a more coherent shared understanding of the current tactical situation.

Figure 3 gives an intuitive picture of this idea. A player can only observe nearby teammates, opponents, ball-related information, and part of the local game geometry. As a result, quantities such as the team center, orientation, compactness, or tactical mode cannot be directly measured by a single player. They have to be inferred by combining local information across the team, which naturally leads to a distributed estimation layer before the control layer.

C. Task-Dependent Relational Formation

Instead of representing the formation as a fixed absolute template, we model it as a task-dependent relational structure. Let

$$\sigma(k) \in \mathcal{S}$$

denote the current tactical task, where \mathcal{S} may include modes such as defend, press, transition, or build-up. For each task, we define a weighted tactical graph

$$G_\sigma(k) = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}_\sigma(k), W_\sigma(k)).$$

Here, an edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}_\sigma(k)$ means that the relation between players i and j is tactically important under the current task. The desired spacing and the importance of this relation are denoted by

$$d_{ij}(\sigma(k)) \quad \text{and} \quad w_{ij}(\sigma(k)),$$

respectively.

Based on this graph, the relational formation error is defined as

$$e_{ij}(k) = \|p_i(k) - p_j(k)\| - d_{ij}(\sigma(k)). \quad (1)$$

$$J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k)) = \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_\sigma(k)} w_{ij}(\sigma(k)) e_{ij}^2(k). \quad (2)$$

This objective measures how well the current team geometry matches the desired task-dependent relational structure.

The main point here is that the formation is no longer described by a rigid set of target coordinates. Instead, it is described by a collection of important tactical relations. This makes the model more realistic for soccer, because the team is allowed to shift, stretch, or reorganize when the tactical context changes, while still preserving an internally meaningful structure.

D. Role-Dependent Feasible Sets

In real soccer, players cannot move freely only to reduce formation error. Their movement is limited by role responsibility, field geometry, and physical or tactical feasibility. For example, a center back should not destroy the defensive line just to stay closer to a teammate, and a defensive midfielder should not completely leave the central protection area.

To describe this, we assign each player a role-dependent feasible set

$$\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k)) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2,$$

and require

$$p_i(k) \in \mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k)).$$

This set can be viewed as the intersection of several constraints:

$$\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k)) = \mathcal{X}_{i,\text{field}} \cap \mathcal{X}_{i,\text{role}}(\sigma(k)) \cap \mathcal{X}_{i,\text{safety}}(k),$$

where $\mathcal{X}_{i,\text{field}}$ represents the field boundary, $\mathcal{X}_{i,\text{role}}(\sigma(k))$ represents the role or tactical zone, and $\mathcal{X}_{i,\text{safety}}(k)$ captures spacing or physical limits.

Figure 4 shows the idea of role-dependent feasibility through several typical roles. The feasible movement region of a center back, a defensive midfielder, and a fullback are different, even if they all try to support the same team objective. This is exactly why local control in soccer cannot be a simple consensus rule. Any reasonable local update must also respect role feasibility.

E. Final Problem Statement

The final problem is to design a distributed estimation-control law for task-driven formation reconfiguration. Using only local observations and neighbor information, each player should estimate the latent team state, update the task-dependent relational graph, and adjust its position to reduce the formation error while staying inside its feasible set.

More specifically, the goal is to achieve the following objectives at the same time:

- reduce the relational formation error $J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))$;
- reduce the disagreement among local team-state estimates $\Psi_G(\hat{\xi}(k))$;

Fig. 4. Example of role-dependent feasible sets. Different roles correspond to different admissible movement regions, which shows why local control must respect tactical feasibility rather than blindly follow neighbor agreement.

- maintain role feasibility through the constraints $p_i(k) \in \mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))$.

In addition, the coach is allowed to influence the tactical graph, but only in a bounded and realistic way. We write

$$W_\sigma(k) = W_\sigma^0(k) + \Delta W_{\text{coach}}(k),$$

with the constraint

$$\|\Delta W_{\text{coach}}(k)\|_F \leq \epsilon,$$

which means that the coach can shape the tactical priorities and interaction weights, but cannot arbitrarily override the players' local decision-making.

Therefore, the problem considered in this report is not centralized formation tracking. Instead, it is a distributed task-driven formation reconfiguration problem under local information, role constraints, and bounded coaching influence.

III. MAIN RESULTS

A. Overview of the Proposed Framework

The main idea of this report is that task-driven formation reconfiguration should not be treated as a simple point-tracking problem. In real soccer, players do not directly know the full global team state, and they also do not move toward fixed target positions in a rigid way. Instead, they first form a local understanding of the current situation, then update the important tactical relations under the current task, and finally adjust their positions while respecting role feasibility.

Based on this idea, I propose a three-layer distributed estimation-control framework. The first layer is a distributed estimation layer, where each player uses local observations and neighbor communication to estimate the current team state. The second layer is a task-dependent graph update layer, where the current tactical graph is updated according to the estimated team state and the current game task. The third layer is a projected local control layer, where each player adjusts its position to reduce relational formation error while staying inside a role-dependent feasible set.

In short, the overall information flow can be written as

local observations \rightarrow distributed estimation \rightarrow tactical graph update \rightarrow pr

This structure is useful because it separates the problem into three more manageable parts: state understanding, tactical structure generation, and constrained local execution.

B. Distributed Estimation of Team State

As defined in the previous section, let the latent team state be

$$\xi(k) = \begin{bmatrix} c(k) \\ \psi(k) \\ \ell(k) \\ \theta(k) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $c(k)$ is the team center, $\psi(k)$ is the formation orientation, $\ell(k)$ represents compactness or shape parameters, and $\theta(k)$ denotes the tactical mode or strategy parameter.

Each player only receives a local observation

$$y_i(k) = H_i(k)\xi(k) + v_i^{\text{obs}}(k),$$

so no single player can directly reconstruct the full team state. A natural way to combine the local information is to formulate a distributed least-squares problem:

$$\min_{\xi} \sum_{i=1}^n \|H_i(k)\xi - y_i(k)\|^2.$$

This objective means that the team tries to find a common estimate that is consistent with the local observations of all players.

To implement this idea in a distributed way, a simple local update can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\xi}_i(k+1) &= \hat{\xi}_i(k) - \alpha_\xi H_i^\top(k)(H_i(k)\hat{\xi}_i(k) - y_i(k)) \\ &\quad + \beta_\xi \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i(k)} a_{ij}(k)(\hat{\xi}_j(k) - \hat{\xi}_i(k)). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha_\xi > 0$ is the local correction step size and $\beta_\xi > 0$ is the consensus gain. The second term uses local observations to correct the estimate, while the third term uses neighbor communication to reduce disagreement among players.

This update is not meant to be the only possible estimator, but it clearly shows the structure we want. Each player combines two types of information: what it sees locally and what it receives from neighboring teammates. If this layer works well, the team can gradually build a shared understanding of the current formation center, orientation, compactness, and tactical situation.

C. Task-Dependent Tactical Graph Update

After the distributed estimation step, the next question is how to update the desired team structure. In this report, the formation is not treated as a fixed absolute template. Instead, it is represented by a task-dependent tactical graph

$$\mathcal{G}_\sigma(k) = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}_\sigma(k), W_\sigma(k)),$$

where $\sigma(k) \in \mathcal{S}$ denotes the current tactical task.

Algorithm Flow of the Proposed Main-Results Framework

Fig. 5. Algorithm flow of the proposed main-results framework. The framework starts from local observations, performs distributed estimation of the team state, identifies the current tactical task, updates the relational tactical graph, and then applies projected local control to achieve formation reconfiguration. The coach acts as a bounded meta-designer by shaping task priorities, graph weights, and role constraints.

The task itself can be viewed as a function of the estimated team state:

$$\sigma(k) = \Gamma(\hat{\xi}_i(k)).$$

For example, depending on the estimated context, the tactical mode may be interpreted as defend, press, transition, or build-up.

Once the task is identified, the desired distances and tactical weights are updated as

$$d_{ij} = d_{ij}(\sigma(k)), \quad w_{ij} = w_{ij}(\sigma(k)).$$

This means that both the desired spacing and the importance of the relation between player i and player j may change with the current tactical task.

Under this model, define the relative displacement and edge error as

$$\Delta p_{ij}(k) = p_i(k) - p_j(k), \quad (4)$$

and

$$e_{ij}(k) = \|\Delta p_{ij}(k)\| - d_{ij}(\sigma(k)). \quad (5)$$

Then the relational formation error can be written compactly as

$$J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k)) = \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_\sigma(k)} w_{ij}(\sigma(k)) e_{ij}^2(k). \quad (6)$$

This quantity measures how far the current team geometry is from the desired task-dependent relational structure.

The main advantage of this formulation is that it is flexible. In a defending phase, the graph can emphasize compactness among center backs and the defensive midfielder. In a pressing phase, the important relations may shift toward the front line and nearby midfield support. Therefore, the team does not try to keep one rigid shape all the time. Instead, it keeps the right internal structure for the current task.

D. Projected Relational Formation Control

Once the tactical graph has been updated, each player needs a local rule to adjust its position. A natural starting point is to reduce the relational formation error by moving along the negative gradient direction. Without constraints, this gives the tentative update

$$\bar{p}_i(k+1) = p_i(k) - \alpha_p \nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k)),$$

where $\alpha_p > 0$ is a step size.

For the formation error defined above, define the unit relative direction

$$q_{ij}(k) = \frac{\Delta p_{ij}(k)}{\|\Delta p_{ij}(k)\|}. \quad (7)$$

Then the local gradient with respect to player i becomes

$$\nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}} = 2 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^\sigma(k)} w_{ij}(\sigma(k)) e_{ij}(k) q_{ij}(k). \quad (8)$$

This is an important point of the model: player i only needs information from its tactical neighbors. Therefore, the control law remains local and does not require full global state knowledge.

However, this unconstrained update is still not enough for soccer, because a player cannot move freely just to reduce formation error. To enforce role feasibility, I use a projected update:

$$p_i(k+1) = \Pi_{\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))} [p_i(k) - \alpha_p \nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))],$$

where $\Pi_{\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))}(\cdot)$ denotes projection onto the feasible set of player i .

This projected control law is the core of the framework. The gradient term tells the player how to move in order to improve the team structure, while the projection term makes sure that the player still respects role-dependent tactical constraints. In other words, the player adjusts locally, but does not abandon its tactical responsibility.

E. Coach as a Bounded Meta-Designer

A key idea of this project is that the coach should not be modeled as a centralized controller who directly commands every player at every instant. That would not be realistic for soccer, and it would also go against the distributed nature of the problem.

Instead, the coach is modeled as a bounded meta-designer. The coach influences the team by shaping tactical priorities, graph weights, and feasibility structure, but the actual execution is still carried out locally by the players. Mathematically, this can be written as

$$W_\sigma(k) = W_\sigma^0(k) + \Delta W_{\text{coach}}(k),$$

where $W_\sigma^0(k)$ is the baseline tactical graph and $\Delta W_{\text{coach}}(k)$ is the coach-induced adjustment.

To keep this influence realistic, the adjustment is assumed to satisfy

$$\|\Delta W_{\text{coach}}(k)\|_F \leq \epsilon,$$

which means that the coach can shape the structure, but only within bounded authority. We may also require

$$\Delta w_{ij}(k) = 0, \quad (i, j) \notin \mathcal{E}_{\text{feasible}}(k),$$

so that the coach cannot introduce arbitrary or unrealistic tactical links. In addition, the weights remain bounded:

$$0 \leq w_{ij}(k) \leq \bar{w}_{ij}.$$

This interpretation fits soccer better. The coach designs the conditions under which distributed coordination happens, but the players still execute the actual decisions locally on the field.

Algorithm 1 Distributed Task-Driven Formation Reconfiguration

- 1: **Input:** local observations $y_i(k)$, neighbor set $\mathcal{N}_i(k)$, feasible set $\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))$
- 2: **Initialize:** $p_i(0)$, $\hat{\xi}_i(0)$, baseline graph $W_\sigma^0(0)$
- 3: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T - 1$ **do**
- 4: Each player collects local observation $y_i(k)$.
- 5: Update local estimate $\hat{\xi}_i(k)$ using local information and neighbor communication.
- 6: Determine or update the current tactical task $\sigma(k)$.
- 7: Update the tactical graph $\mathcal{G}_\sigma(k)$, including $d_{ij}(\sigma(k))$ and $w_{ij}(\sigma(k))$.
- 8: Compute the local gradient $\nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))$.
- 9: Perform projected position update:

$$p_i(k+1) = \Pi_{\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))} [p_i(k) - \alpha_p \nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))].$$

- 10: Apply bounded coach shaping to the graph if needed.
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: **Output:** reconfigured player positions $p_i(k)$ and distributed team-state estimates $\hat{\xi}_i(k)$
-

F. Expected Properties and Interpretation

The framework above is designed to have several useful properties.

First, it is *locally implementable*. Each player only needs its own local observation $y_i(k)$, the estimates shared by neighboring teammates, and the positions of tactically connected neighbors. This makes the framework consistent with the fact that players do not have full global information during the match.

Second, it is *task-adaptive*. Because both d_{ij} and w_{ij} depend on the current task $\sigma(k)$, the desired formation can change with the game situation. This is more realistic than forcing the team to maintain one rigid template all the time.

Third, it is *feasibility-preserving*. Since the local control law uses projection, every update satisfies

$$p_i(k+1) \in \mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k)).$$

This means the player will not reduce formation error at the cost of completely breaking its role responsibility.

Finally, the framework gives a reasonable interpretation of formation recovery. If the estimation disagreement $\Psi_{\mathcal{G}}(\hat{\xi}(k))$ is reduced over time and the projected local control lowers the relational formation error $J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))$, then the team should gradually recover a compact and tactically meaningful structure. Therefore, the result of the framework is not only better geometric organization, but also better shared tactical understanding.

IV. SIMULATIONS

A. Simulation Setting

To verify the proposed framework, I use a small numerical simulation based on a five-player defensive block. The simulation is not intended to reproduce a full professional soccer match. Instead, it is used as a simple test case to check whether the proposed estimation-control structure can generate

the expected qualitative behavior: formation recovery, task-driven reconfiguration, and agreement in the estimated team state.

The five players are

$$\mathcal{V} = \{LB, CB_1, CB_2, RB, DM\},$$

where LB and RB are the two fullbacks, CB_1 and CB_2 are the two center backs, and DM is the defensive midfielder. The player positions are defined in a two-dimensional field coordinate system:

$$p_i(k) = \begin{bmatrix} x_i(k) \\ y_i(k) \end{bmatrix}.$$

The proposed projected relational update is used in the simulation:

$$p_i(k+1) = \Pi_{\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))} [p_i(k) - \alpha_p \nabla_{p_i} J_{\text{form}}(p(k), \sigma(k))].$$

Here, J_{form} is the task-dependent relational formation error, and $\mathcal{X}_i(\sigma(k))$ is the role-dependent feasible set of player i .

To make the comparison more meaningful, I compare three methods:

- **Absolute anchor baseline:** each player moves toward a fixed desired position.
- **Relational graph control:** players reduce the relational distance error without the full task-driven estimation-control structure.
- **Proposed framework:** players use the task-dependent relational graph and projected local control under role feasibility constraints.

B. Scenario 1: Defensive Compactness Recovery

The first scenario tests whether the team can recover from a disturbed defensive formation. The left plot in Fig. 6 shows the ideal compact defensive block. Then, a disturbance is added to the players' positions, producing the disorganized formation shown in the middle plot. The proposed method is then applied to recover the formation.

From Fig. 6, the proposed method successfully moves the players back into a compact and organized structure. The result is not exactly a rigid return to the original coordinates, but it recovers the important tactical relations among the fullbacks, center backs, and defensive midfielder. This is consistent with the relational formation idea used in the report.

The decay of the formation error is shown in Fig. 7. All three methods eventually reduce the error, but the relational graph control and the proposed framework reduce the error much faster at the beginning. This is reasonable because these two methods directly control the important pairwise tactical relations, instead of only pulling each player back to an absolute target point.

This result supports the main modeling choice of this report. For a soccer formation, the relative structure among players is often more important than exact absolute coordinates. Therefore, controlling the relational formation error gives a more natural way to describe compactness recovery.

C. Scenario 2: Fullback Pressing Reconfiguration

The second scenario tests whether the framework can handle a task-driven formation change. At the beginning, the team stays in a defending mode. Then the left fullback LB steps forward to press. This creates a new tactical situation: the center backs and defensive midfielder should adjust their positions to cover the space behind the fullback and preserve the defensive structure.

In this case, the tactical task switches from defend to press:

$$\sigma(k) : \text{defend} \rightarrow \text{press}.$$

After the switch, the desired distances and tactical weights are updated:

$$d_{ij} = d_{ij}(\sigma(k)), \quad w_{ij} = w_{ij}(\sigma(k)).$$

Thus, the target formation is not fixed. The formation itself changes according to the current task.

Figure 8 shows this process. Before the task switch, the team keeps a normal defensive block. When LB presses forward, the formation becomes temporarily unbalanced. After the reconfiguration process, CB_1 , CB_2 , RB , and DM adjust their relative positions and form a new compact structure behind the pressing fullback.

This scenario is important because it shows the difference between formation maintenance and formation reconfiguration. The goal is not always to return to the original shape. In many soccer situations, the better behavior is to move into a new structure that matches the current task. This is why the task-dependent graph formulation is useful.

D. Distributed Estimation Result

The simulation also includes a simple distributed estimation layer. Each player maintains an estimate of the latent team state, and neighboring players exchange their estimates. The disagreement among local estimates is measured by

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{G}}(\hat{\xi}(k)) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}(k)} \|\hat{\xi}_i(k) - \hat{\xi}_j(k)\|^2.$$

As shown in Fig. 9, the estimation disagreement decreases quickly and approaches zero after only a few iterations. This supports the idea that the players can form a shared understanding of the team state through local observation and neighbor communication. In the context of this project, this shared estimate is necessary before the team can update the tactical graph and reconfigure the formation in a coordinated way.

E. Evaluation Metrics and Discussion

The simulations are evaluated using three main metrics. The first metric is the relational formation error:

$$J_{\text{form}}(k) = \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}_{\sigma}(k)} w_{ij}(\sigma(k)) (\|p_i(k) - p_j(k)\| - d_{ij}(\sigma(k)))^2.$$

This measures whether the team keeps the desired pairwise tactical relations.

Fig. 6. Scenario 1: defensive compactness recovery. The left panel shows the ideal defensive block, the middle panel shows the disturbed initial formation, and the right panel shows the recovered formation generated by the proposed framework.

Fig. 7. Scenario 1: decay of the relational formation error $J_{\text{form}}(k)$ for three methods. The proposed framework and relational graph control show faster early-stage recovery than the absolute anchor baseline.

The second metric is the recovery time:

$$T_{\text{rec}} = \min\{k : J_{\text{form}}(k) \leq \varepsilon\}.$$

This measures how quickly the team returns to an acceptable level of compactness after a disturbance.

The third metric is the estimation disagreement:

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{G}}(\hat{\xi}(k)) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}(k)} \|\hat{\xi}_i(k) - \hat{\xi}_j(k)\|^2.$$

This measures whether the players share a consistent understanding of the latent team state.

Overall, the simulation results support the main idea of the report. The proposed framework can recover a compact defensive structure after disturbance, and it can also reconfigure the formation when the task changes. More importantly, the method does not rely on a centralized controller. Each player only uses local information, neighbor communication, and role-dependent feasible sets. This matches the way soccer coordination is naturally distributed on the field.

V. CONCLUSION

This report studied soccer formation coordination as a distributed multi-agent problem. Compared with the midterm

formulation, the main step forward is that formation is no longer treated as a fixed absolute template. Instead, I model it as a task-dependent relational structure, where important player-to-player tactical relations are represented by graph edges, desired distances, and task-dependent weights.

The proposed framework combines distributed estimation, tactical graph update, and projected local control. The distributed estimation layer allows players to form a shared understanding of the latent team state from local observations. The tactical graph update layer changes the desired relational structure according to the current task. The projected local control layer then reduces formation error while keeping each player inside its role-dependent feasible set. In this framework, the coach acts as a bounded meta-designer, shaping graph weights, task priorities, and constraints without directly controlling every player.

The simulation results support this framework at a conceptual level. In the defensive compactness recovery scenario, the relational control terms reduce formation error and recover a compact defensive block. In the fullback pressing scenario, the team does not simply return to the original shape, but reconfigures into a new task-consistent structure. The estimation disagreement also decreases quickly, which suggests that local communication can help players form a coherent estimate of the current team state.

There are several directions for future work. First, the ball and opponents should be included as active dynamic components rather than only background disturbances. Second, real tracking data could be used to estimate tactical graph weights, desired distances, and task-switching rules. Third, the player model can be improved by adding velocity, acceleration, fatigue, and physical limits. Finally, learning-based methods such as multi-agent reinforcement learning could be used to learn the task-switching map or adapt the tactical graph online. The long-term goal is not to replace human tactical understanding, but to provide a mathematical language for studying how team structure, information flow, and coaching constraints interact in football.

Fig. 8. Scenario 2: fallback pressing reconfiguration. The left panel shows the original defending structure. The middle panel shows the task switch when the left fullback presses forward. The right panel shows the reconfigured structure after the projected relational control update.

Fig. 9. Distributed estimation disagreement over time. The fast decay of $\Psi_{\mathcal{G}}(\hat{\xi}(k))$ indicates that players quickly form a consistent estimate of the latent team state.

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Football has always been one of the most meaningful parts of my life. I love this sport, and it has changed not only my daily life, but also the way I understand teamwork, structure, competition, and the world around me. Multi-agent systems provide me with another lens to look at football. Through this project, I tried to use ideas from consensus, distributed estimation, graph theory, and constrained control to explain what may happen behind team coordination on the field.

This project is still an early exploration, but I feel happy and proud that I could connect my academic interests with something I truly care about. I am thankful for this course, for the guidance I received, and for the chance to develop a project that is both technical and personal to me.

VI. INFO

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